

Deliverable

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D5.3 - Content Production

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Abstract:

This document will define for each iteration the evaluation methodology to be followed, based on the requirements. It will establish what elements will be evaluated and the calendar of evaluation activities.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	18-05-2018	Zora Schärer Kalkandjiev	RBB	Structure, ToC and Introduction
0.2	05-06-2018	Zora Schärer Kalkandjiev	RBB	First example for content description
0.3	03-08-2018	Francesc Mas	CCMA	Added content
0.4	21-08-2018	Zora Schärer Kalkandjiev	RBB	Included feedback of reviewer
0.5	18-09-2018	Zora Schärer Kalkandjiev	RBB	Restructuring and refining
1.0	04-10-2018	Zora Schärer Kalkandjiev	RBB	Final version

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Statement of originality:

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ImAc follows a user centered design approach. The project developments must be driven by real user needs, continuously involving these users in every step of the design and implementation. The solutions developed in the project are piloted and validated in trials, ensuring market relevance and user acceptance.

D5.3 is the delivery of the content needed for these demonstration pilots. This document lists all content that will be used in the tests and for demo purposes. In the second iteration of this document, the content used for the cross-national pilot and the pilot phase 2 will be added.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
AD	Audio description
AST	Audio subtitles
D	Deliverable
FOV	Field of view
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMD	Head-mounted display
HUR	Home User Requirements
HQ	High quality
ImAc	Immersive Accessibility
LQ	Low quality
M	Month
MS	Milestone
PUR	Professional User Requirements
SL	Sign Language
T	Task
VR	Virtual Reality

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of this document

This document describes the content produced for the demonstration pilots (for each of its two iterations). It is essentially linked to the content itself, which is part of MS8.

This document describes the content to be developed under WP5 and used in demonstration pilots. Pilot actions are understood as any test in which ImAc services and products are demonstrated and feedback from users is gathered.

The main aim of WP5 is to test the ImAc services and products (many of them in two iterations) by using suitable content that is similar to the content consumed in typical use cases and that meets the technical requirements of the ImAc framework. The production of content is thus essential, since the outcome of WP5 feeds into several other project WPs (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Diagram of relation between work packages, and its cycles (iterations).

1.2. Scope of this document

ImAc follows a user-centric design, which means that technological components, services and tools are developed based on user requirements. These developments are evaluated where appropriate in different iterations, guaranteeing the participation of end users at different stages in the process.

This deliverable describes the content used for the demonstration pilots. The requirements for the content are described in section 2. A short overview of all content is given in section 3, while the properties of all media files are listed in detail in section 4.

1.3. Status of this document

This is the first version of D5.3 with delivery foreseen in M11. A revised version of this document will be delivered in M25.

This document presents the content for the first phase of the Spanish and German pilots (pilot phase 1). The content for the second phase of the Spanish and German pilots (pilot phase 2) as well as the cross-national pilot will be presented in the final updated version of this document.

1.4. Relation with other ImAc activities

D5.3 originates from ‘T2.2 User Requirements’, which feeds into ‘T5.1 Execution and Evaluation Plan’, and impacts on all WP5 tasks, as shown in Figure 2.

D5.3 is the basis for the future ‘T5.3 German Pilot’, ‘T5.4 Spanish Pilot’ and ‘T5.5 Cross-national Pilot’, which will feed into ‘T5.6 Evaluation’ and result in ‘D5.4 Pilot evaluation report’.

Figure 2: Diagram of tasks and outcomes (deliverables)

2. GUIDELINES FOR CONTENT PRODUCTION

As a first step, guidelines for the production of content used for the demonstration pilots were developed.

Regarding the 360°-video content (see section 2.1) there are minimum technical specifications as well as content- and production-related requirements that need to be met. The definition of the technical properties is a result of the specifications in D3.1 Architecture and Design. The definition of the content- and production- related properties is a result of general guidelines for 360° videos as well as requirements which have to be met in order to follow the pilot evaluation plan specified in D5.2. For example, if guiding mechanisms are to be tested for the subtitle and sign language services, there need to be speakers in different fields of view (FOVs).

Regarding the ImAc content (see section 2.2), i.e. the accessibility content, there are again technical specifications resulting from D3.1 as well as editorial properties resulting from the user requirements presented in D2.2.

2.1. Properties of 360° video content

Technical properties	
Ratio	Webplayer: 16:9 HMD: 1:1
HQ resolution (minimum)	2160x1280 for the equirectangular frame.
LQ resolution	FullHD (1280x720) for the equirectangular frame
Duration (minimum)	5 minutes per clip for each condition that is tested, clips need to be comparable in form and content (see D5.2)
File format	Video: H264 / Audio: AAC

Table 1: Technical properties of video content

Content-/ Production-related properties	
Relevant for...	Property
All	Movement of the camera is avoided
All	Cameras are centred on main action to avoid stitching errors in the area of the main action
SUB / SL	There is more than one speaker
SUB / SL	At least two speakers are spatially wide apart (different FOVs) or at least one speaker moves into different FOVs
SUB / SL	Camera position is preferably at eye level of speakers (natural position)
SUB / SL	Close-ups of speakers are avoided
SUB / SL	Lip movements of speakers are visible
AD	Activity/sound comes from different directions
AD	Audio track is available in 3D-formats (ambisonics, binaural), see HUR.02.38.0 and HUR.03.06.0

Table 2: Content- and production related properties of video content

2.2. Properties of ImAc content

Technical		
Service	Property	Requirement
SUB	File format of subtitle file is TTML	
SL	File format of signer video is H264	
SL	Ratio of signer video is 1:1	
SL	Resolution of Signer video is ... (to be specified for pilot phase 2)	HUR.02.20.0
AD	File format for AD files is AAC	
AD	AD tracks are available in different spatial formats (stereo, ambisonics, binaural)	HUR.03.40.01 / HUR.03.42.01

Table 3: Technical properties of ImAc content

Editorial		
Service	Property	Requirement
SUB	Subtitles are available as an alternative stream in simple language	HUR.03.04.0 (priority: COULD; pilot 2)
SUB	Colour coding is introduced for all new speakers	PUR.03.11.0 (priority: MUST; pilot 1 &

		pilot 2)
SUB	Non-speech information is presented with icons	HUR.02.32.0 / HUR.03.03.0 (priority: COULD; pilot 2)
SL	The body shift traditionally used to indicate different speakers by SL interpreters is avoided	outcome of pre-pilot test (pilot 2)
SUB/SL	Angle information for each speaker is defined	PUR.01.08.02 / PUR.01.09.02 (priority: SHOULD; pilot 1 & pilot 2)
SUB/SL	Guiding mechanism is omitted for very short speech phrases	PUR.01.08.01 / PUR.01.09.01 (priority: MUST; pilot 1 & pilot 2)
AD	Angle information is provided for the content being described	HUR.03.40.01 / HUR.02.44.0 / HUR.02.45.0 (priority: SHOULD; cross-national pilot)
AD	Main and secondary actions are described by two different voices	HUR.03.07.0 (priority: COULD; cross-national pilot)

Table 4: Editorial properties of ImAc content

3. LIST OF CONTENT DATA SETS

The following table lists the content data sets that were created to be used for demo purposes or pilot actions. In the second iteration of this document, more content will be added to the list, mainly to be used for the cross-national pilot and pilot phase 2. Already at this stage there are three content data sets that are planned for these future pilot actions: C08 - C11 (since the actual files for these datasets do not exist yet, they are not listed in section 4). The last data set is the result of a cooperation with the US-American company RYOT (part of Yahoo), giving the ImAc project the opportunity to widen its horizon of dissemination.

Name	Description	Used / planned for	Content owner	Content type
C01	Recording of an interview during a radio show in the studio of Radio Fritz (RBB)	Pre-pilot test	RBB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° video • Subtitles • Signer
C02	Documentary: Making-of video of the RBB news show "Abendschau"	Demo	RBB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° video • Subtitles
C03	Opera: "Romeo & Juliet" Scene 1	Demo	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° video • Subtitles • Signer • Immersive audio
C04	Opera: "Romeo & Juliet" Scene 2	Demo	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° video • Subtitles • Immersive audio
C05	Music Concert: ICat Desconcert Theme 1	Demo	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° 3D video • Subtitles • Immersive audio
C06	Music Concert: ICat Desconcert Theme 2	Pilot 1	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° 3D video • Subtitles • Immersive audio
C07	Fiction: Short film about an AI-robot created after the sci-fi writer Philip K. Dick	Pilot 1	ARTE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° video • Subtitles

C08	Documentary: Making-of video of the News daily program at TV3	Planned for cross-national pilot	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360°3D video • Subtitles • Immersive audio • Audio description
C09	Documentary: Making-of video of the FAQS (“Preguntes Freqüents”) debate program at TV3	Planned for cross-national pilot	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360°3D video • Subtitles • Immersive audio • Audio description
C10	Short film: Polonia (Catalan humour programme at TV3 (Spain))	Planned for cross-national pilot	CCMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360°3D video • Subtitles • Immersive audio • Audio description
C11	Comedy show	Planned for additional pilot action	RYOT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 360° video • Subtitles

Table 5: Content data sets used for demo purposes and pilot actions

4. CONTENT DESCRIPTION

The following tables describe in detail each content data set. All the files of a data set are listed together with their technical properties.

4.1. C01

File name(s)	360°video: 1) RBB_Rapzember_H264_1140x720_audio strereo.mp4 Subtitles: 2) RBB_Rapzember_subtitles_DE.xml 3) RBB_Rapzember_subtitles_CAT.xml Signer video: 4) RBB_Rapzember_signer_DE.mp4
Duration	00:03:10
Restrictions for usage	No restrictions, but always must be referenced as RBB content.
Example frames	
360° video	
Content description	Recording of an interview with the Musician Young Hurn in the studio of Radio Fritz / RBB. Two speakers sitting opposite each other.
Content language(s)	German
File size	31.7 MB
File format	MP4
Codec	H264/AVC

Coding profile	Main@L3	
Bit rate	1.3 MB/s	
Frame rate	30 fps	
Frame rate mode	Constant	
Chroma subsampling	4:2:0	
Bit depth	8 bits	
Resolution	1440x720	
Projection	Equirectangular	
Audio format	AAC	
No. of channels	2	
Audio bit depth	32 bits	
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz	
Subtitles		
File size	2) 17 KB	3) 14 KB
File format	EBU-TT-D	
Language(s)	2) German	3) Catalan
Signer video		
File size	52 MB	
File format	MP4	
Codec	H264/AVC	
Coding profile	High@L3.1	
Bit rate	1.9 MB/s	
Frame rate	50 fps	
Frame rate mode	Constant	

Chroma subsampling	4:2:0
Bit depth	8 bits
Resolution	720x720

4.2. C02

File name(s)	<p>360°video:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) RBB_Abendschau_short_H264_4K_audio stereo.mp4 2) RBB_Abendschau_short_H264_1280x640_audio stereo.pm4 <p>Subtitles:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3) RBB_Abendschau_short_DE.xml
Duration	00:01:46
Restrictions for usage	Request permission for public usage.
Example frames	
360° video	

Content description	Making-of video of the RBB news show "Abendschau", several shots in different places (studio, outside, production room etc.), one main on-screen speaker, few short additional on-screen speakers	
Content language(s)	German	
File size	1) 130 MB	2) 127 MB
File format	MP4	
Codec	H264/AVC	
Coding profile	1) Main@L5.1	2) Main@L3.1
Bit rate	1) 10.3 MB/s	2) 10.1 MB/s
Frame rate	30 fps	
Frame rate mode	Constant	
Chroma subsampling	4:2:0	
Bit depth	8 bits	
Resolution	1) 4096 x 2048	2) 1280x640
Projection	Equirectangular	
Audio format	AAC	
No. of channels	2	
Audio bit depth	32 bits	
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz	
Subtitles		
File size	13 KB	
File format	EBU-TT-D	
Language(s)	German	

4.3. C03

File name(s)	<p>360°video:</p> <p>1) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_H265_6400x3200_AMBIX1STAAC.mp4</p> <p>2) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_H264_3840x2160_AMBIX1STAAC.mp4</p> <p>Subtitles:</p> <p>3) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_subtitles_EN.xml</p> <p>4) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_subtitles_CAT.xml</p> <p>5) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_subtitles_CAST.xml</p> <p>6) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_subtitles_DE.xml</p> <p>Signer video:</p> <p>7) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_signer_EN.mov</p> <p>8) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_signer_CAT.mov</p> <p>9) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_signer_CAST.mov</p> <p>10) CCMA_OPERALICEU01_signer_DE.mp4</p>
Duration	00:08:29
Restrictions for usage	Request permission for public usage
Example frames	

360° video		
Content description	Opera “Romeo & Julietta” at Liceu Theater (Barcelona) with 360° video content and Ambisonic audio.	
Content language(s)	French	
File size	1) 3.08 GB	2) 2.29 GB
File format	MP4	
Codec	H264/AVC	
Coding profile	1) Main@L6	2) High@L5.1
Bit rate	1) 48.4 MB/s	2) 36 MB/s
Frame rate	25 fps	
Frame rate mode	Constant	
Chroma subsampling	4:2:0	
Bit depth	8 bits	
Resolution	1) 6400x3200	2) 3840x2160
Projection	Equirectangular	
Audio format	AAC	
No. of channels	4 (1 st order ambisonic)	

Audio bit depth	32 bits			
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz			
Subtitles				
File size	3) 18 KB	4) 17 KB	5) 17 KB	6) 18 KB
File format	EBU-TT-D			
Language(s)	3) English	4) Catalan	5) Spanish	6) German
Signer video				
Language(s)	3) English	4) Catalan	5) Spanish	6) German
File size	7) 3.95 GB	8) 3.21 GB	9) 3.83	10) 609 MB
File format	7) MOV	8) MOV	9) MOV	10) MP4
Codec	7) ProRes	8) ProRes	9) ProRes	10) H264/AVC
Coding profile	7) ProRes 422 HQ	8) ProRes 422 HQ	9) ProRes 422 HQ	10) High@L3.1
Bit rate	7) 68.1 MB/s	8) 55.4 MB/s	9) 66.1 MB/s	10) 1.9 MB/s
Frame rate	7) 30 fps	8) 24 fps	9) 30 fps	10) 25 fps
Frame rate mode	Constant			
Chroma subsampling	4:2:2			
Bit depth	8 bits			
Resolution	7) 1080x720	8) 1080x720	9) 1080x720	10) 600x600

4.4. C04

File name(s)	360°video: 1) CCMA_OPERALICEU02_PRORES_6400x3200_AMBIX1STWAV.mov 2) CCMA_OPERALICEU02_H264_1920x1080_STEREOAAC.mov Subtitles: 3) CCMA_OPERALICEU02_subtitles_CAT.xml 4) CCMA_OPERALICEU02_subtitles_DE.xml
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Duration	00:08:15	
Restrictions for usage	Request permission for public usage	
Example frames		
360° video		
Content description	Opera "Romeo & Julietta" at Liceu Theater (Barcelona) with 360° video content and Ambisonic audio.	
Content language(s)	French	
File size	1) 52.48 GB	2) 274.2 MB
File format	MOV	
Codec	ProRes	
Coding profile	1) ProRes 422 HQ	2) High@L4

Bit rate	1) 848 MB/s	2) 4.4 MB/s
Frame rate	25 fps	
Frame rate mode	Constant	
Chroma subsampling	4:2:2	
Bit depth	8 bits	
Resolution	1) 6400x3200	2) 1920x080
Projection	Equirectangular	
Audio format	AAC	
No. of channels	4 (1 st order ambisonic)	
Audio bit depth	32 bits	
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz	
Subtitles		
File size	3) 8 KB	4) 8 KB
File format	EBU-TT-D	
Language(s)	3) Catalan	4) German

4.5. C05

File name(s)	<p>360°video:</p> <p>1) CCMA_Desconcert Marion Harrier Havana_PRORES422HQ_4096x4096_AMBIX1STORDERWAV.mov</p> <p>2) CCMA_Desconcert Marion Harrier Havana_H264_1280x640_StereoAAC.mp4</p> <p>Subtitles:</p> <p>3) CCMA_Desconcert Marion Harrier Havana_subtitles_CAT.xml</p> <p>4) CCMA_Desconcert Marion Harrier Havana_subtitles_EN.xml</p> <p>5) CCMA_Desconcert Marion Harrier Havana_subtitles_DE.xml</p>
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Duration	00:04:13	
Restrictions for usage	No restrictions, but always must be referenced as CCMA content.	
Example frames		
360° video		
Content description	Musical Concert at Sala Apolo (Barcelona, Spain) with 360 3D video content and Ambisonic audio	
Content language(s)	Catalan	
File size	1) 51.2 GB	2) 348.4 MB
File format	1) MOV	2) MP4
Codec	1) ProRes	2) H264/AVC
Coding profile	1) ProRes 422 HQ	2) HIGH@L3.1
Bit rate	1) 1621 MB/s	2) 11 MB/s

Frame rate	30 fps		
Frame rate mode	Constant		
Chroma subsampling	4:2:2		
Bit depth	8 bits		
Resolution	1) 4096x4096	2) 1280x640	
Projection	Equirectangular		
Audio format	AAC		
No. of channels	4 (1 st order ambisonic)		
Audio bit depth	32 bits		
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz		
Subtitles			
File size	3) 15 KB	4) 16 KB	5) 16 KB
File format	EBU-TT-D		
Language(s)	3) Catalan	4) English	5) German

4.6. C06

File name(s)	<p>360°video:</p> <p>1) CCMA_Desconcert Halldor Mar Leyre_PRORES422HQ_4096x4096_AMIBX1STORDERWAV.mov</p> <p>2) CCMA_Desconcert Halldor Mar Leyre_H264_1280x640_STEREOAAC.mp4</p> <p>Subtitles:</p> <p>3) CCMA_Desconcert Halldor Mar Leyre_subtitles_CAT.xml</p> <p>4) CCMA_Desconcert Halldor Mar Leyre_subtitles_EN.xml</p> <p>5) CCMA_Desconcert Halldor Mar Leyre_subtitles_DE.xml</p>
Duration	00:04:33
Restrictions for usage	No restrictions, but always must be referenced as CCMA content

<p>Example frames</p>		
<p>360° video</p>		
<p>Content description</p>	<p>Musical Concert at Sala Apolo (Barcelona, Spain) with 360° 3D video content and Ambisonic audio</p>	
<p>Content language(s)</p>	<p>Catalan</p>	
<p>File size</p>	<p>1) 52.5 GB</p>	<p>2) 378.2 MB</p>
<p>File format</p>	<p>1) MOV</p>	<p>2) MP4</p>
<p>Codec</p>	<p>1) ProRes</p>	<p>2) H264/AVC</p>
<p>Coding profile</p>	<p>1) ProRes 422 HQ</p>	<p>2) High@L3.1</p>
<p>Bit rate</p>	<p>1) 1535 MB/s</p>	<p>2) 11.1 MB/s</p>
<p>Frame rate</p>	<p>30 fps</p>	
<p>Frame rate mode</p>	<p>Constant</p>	

Chroma subsampling	4:2:2		
Bit depth	8 bits		
Resolution	1) 4096x4096	2) 1280x640	
Projection	Equirectangular		
Audio format	AAC		
No. of channels	4 (1 st order ambisonic)		
Audio bit depth	32 bits		
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz		
Subtitles			
File size	3) 17 KB	4) 17 KB	5) 17 KB
File format	EBU-TT-D		
Language(s)	3) Catalan	4) English	5) German

4.7. C07

File name(s)	360°video: 1) RBB_I Philip_H264_2160x1080_audio stereo.mp4 2) RBB_I Philip_H264_1080x540_audio stereo.pm4 Subtitles: 3) RBB_I Philip_subtitles_EN.xml 4) RBB_I Philip_subtitles_DE.xml 5) RBB_I Philip_subtitles_CAT.xml
Duration	00:14:44
Restrictions for usage	Do not show publicly

Example frames

360° video

Content description	Fictional story about an AI-robot that is created after the sci-fi writer Philip K. Dick and that becomes more and more independent of his programmers. Different scenes with several speakers in different field of views. The viewer has the perspective of the robot.	
Content language(s)	English	
File size	1) 1.01 GB	2) 813 MB
File format	MP4	
Codec	H264/AVC	
Coding profile	1) Main@L5	2) Main@L3.2
Bit rate	1) 9.8 MB/s	2) 7.7 MB/s
Frame rate	60 fps	
Frame rate	Constant	

mode			
Chroma subsampling	4:2:0		
Bit depth	8 bits		
Resolution	1) 4096x2048	2) 1280x640	
Audio format	AAC		
No. of channels	2		
Audio sampling rate	48 kHz		
Subtitles			
File size	3) 41 KB	4) 43 KB	5) 46 KB
File format	EBU-TT-D		
Language(s)	3) English	4) German	5) Catalan

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